

Factors Influencing Digital Banking Satisfaction among Gen Z in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

This study investigated the factors influencing digital banking satisfaction among Generation Z in Sri Lanka. Rapid advancements in Information and Communication Technology have revolutionized banking services, making digital banking increasingly prevalent, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic. Using a quantitative research design, data were collected from 189 respondents aged 20–27 years, primarily students from the Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce at the University of Sri Jayewardenepura. The study employed the Electronic Service Quality Model, the Bank Service Quality Model, and the Technology Acceptance Model to develop a conceptual framework. The data were analyzed using descriptive analysis and Structural Equation Modeling techniques, utilizing SmartPLS4 and SPSS as analytical tools. Findings revealed that ease of use, security, and web design and content significantly influence digital banking satisfaction among Generation Z. However, reliability and information privacy do not have a significant impact. Hypothesis testing confirmed these results, with path model analysis demonstrating the strength of relationships between variables. The findings highlighted critical areas for improvement in digital banking services to enhance customer satisfaction among Generation Z. This research offers valuable insights for policymakers and banking institutions in developing digital business strategies, such as creating regulations that promote seamless digital banking experiences. Additionally, content creators and online service providers can refine their strategies to better align with user expectations, fostering greater adoption and trust in digital banking. By focusing on Generation Z, a dynamic and influential demographic group, this study contributes to Sri Lanka's digital banking landscape by enhancing awareness. However, the study's limitations, including a small sample size, highlight the need for future research incorporating larger and more diverse samples, additional influencing factors, and mixed method approaches to provide a more comprehensive understanding of digital banking satisfaction in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: *Digital Banking, Gen Z, Satisfaction*